

GENDER EQUALITY AND WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN ISLAM

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Abstract: This article provides information about the rights given to women in Islam, marriage, dowry issues, based on which we showed it how the norms related to gender issues in our society are related to Islam. Also, evidence is given that women's rights are more than men's rights in Sharia norms.

Keywords: women, marriage, dowry, gender, Islam, Sharia.

Today, gender issues in our society are one of the issues the focus of our country. Eliminating women's problems, improving women's lifestyles, and increasing their activity in various fields are of great importance.

Women make up half of the world's population. Economic growth can be ensured by involving them in society. Also, their development makes a great contribution to the development of mankind. "It is no coincidence that the UN has introduced another index of humanitarian criteria since 1996. This index is related to ensuring concrete equality between women and men, expanding the rights and opportunities of women, and eliminating gender inequality"¹.

Also, women's rights and not violating their rights are emphasized even in Islam. With women's rights in Islam, some people make inappropriate comments that Islam has restricted women's rights. However, before Islam, the people living in the Arabian Peninsula violated the rights of girls and even buried them alive. The

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Оила ва Меҳнат кодексларининг гендер экспертизаси. – Тошкент: 2008. - Б. 5.

family where a girl child was born would mourn. They would even give it up by burying it alive so as not to cause economic hardship to their family members later.

However, when the religion of Islam appeared in the land of Saudi Arabia, these processes were put to an end. According to the teachings of Islam, more promises were given to families where a girl was born than to a family where a boy was born.

In a hadith narrated by Abu Huraira, may Allah be pleased with him, the following is said:

The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: "Whoever has three daughters and is patient with their hardships and hardships, Allah will enter Paradise because of His mercy to them."

One person:

"What if she has two daughters, O Prophet of God (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him):?" he asked.

They said, "Even if she has two daughters."

One person:

"What if there is only one, O Prophet of God (peace be upon him):?" he asked.

"At least one," they said.²

So, raising a girl child can be the first factor leading to the door of heaven.

In order to have a broader understanding of women's rights in Islam, it is appropriate to first dwell on the examples of family and marriage relations.

In Burhanuddin Marginani's work "Hidaya", they made the following points about equality in marriage:

"Equality in marriage (i.e., that the future groom is financially and spiritually worthy of the girl in Shariat) is taken into account"³.

In order for a boy and a girl to get married, their families should also be worthy of each other. Because one party's financial difficulties can cause problems and

² Исломда аёллар ҳукуқи. <https://islom.uz/maqola/8175>

³ Бурхонуддин Марғинович. Ҳидоя шарҳ бидоятил мубтади: 2-жилд. - Тошкент: Hilol-Nashr, 2020. - Б. 57.

mutual disrespect in their families. Especially if the girl comes from a prestigious family and the boy comes from a greedy family, it undermines equality in marriage. However, if it is the other way around, in such a case, the girl is from a family with financial difficulties is considered insignificant as the breadwinner of the family.

In Islam, scholars of the Hanafi school have listed a number of factors regarding equality in marriage and the good and beautiful continuation of the marriage. These are religion, economy and profession.

Religion refers to a woman's belief, religiousness, and righteousness. Such a woman is no match for a husband who is unfaithful and exposes sinful deeds.

The economic goal is that if the families of the bride and groom are close to each other economically, it will be easier and easier for them to get along.

Occupation and profession mean that the profession of the groom is closer to the profession of the bride's father⁴.

Also, according to the Islamic law, the man who arranges the marriage must give a dowry to the girl to be married. The holy source of Islam, the Qur'an, verse 4 of Surah Nisa: "Give your wives their dowry with pleasure! If they give you something of their own volition, eat it freely and appetite"⁵.

Mahr is a financial payment given to the bride by the groom. The mahr should be property given by the groom himself and not by the groom's parents. This determines his responsibility as the head of the family.

In Islam, the maximum amount of dowry is not clearly defined. However, the hadith of the Prophet Muhammad, who said: "Mahr less than ten dirhams, is not mahr"⁶ serves as a proof that the minimum amount of dowry is set. For ten dirhams, it was possible to get a shield during the time of Prophet Muhammad

Prophet Muhammad did not agree to give his daughter Fatima to Ali without a dowry even when they were giving their daughter Fatima in marriage to Ali.

⁴ Салоҳиддин Муҳиддин. Оила ва шаръий никоҳ одоблари. – Тошкент: Мовароуннахр, 1999. – Б. 28.

⁵ Куръони карим маъноларининг таржимаси: Таржима ва изоҳлар муаллифи Абдулазиз Мансур. – Тошкент: Тошкент ислом университети, 2001. – Б. 77.

⁶ Салоҳиддин Муҳиддин. Оила ва шаръий никоҳ одоблари. – Тошкент: Мовароуннахр, 1999. – Б. 15.

Therefore, in Islam, the consent of both parties and the presence of witnesses and dowry play an important role in marriage.

They divided the term of dowry into two types:

- 1) Mahr to be paid quickly (mu'ajjal);
- 2) Mahr to be given later (muajjal).

Dowry: can be in the form of gold, housing, money.

If a certain number of rooms in a house are given as a dowry, the specified rooms of this house are the property of the woman. If a woman's marriage breaks up for some reason, she has the right to claim her property or to live in those reserved rooms.

Spiritual things are not counted as dowry. Mahr must be in the form of property. It is obligatory to give and receive mahr. The boy has the responsibility to pay the dowry and the girl has the right to demand the dowry.

Based on the information mentioned above, it should be noted that the issue of mahr serves as an important guarantee in preventing the violation of women's rights in Islamic teaching. So, in Islam, women's rights are regulated by very well-developed norms.

REFERENCES:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Оила ва Меҳнат кодексларининг гендер экспертизаси. – Тошкент: 2008.
2. Қуръони карим маъноларининг таржимаси: Таржима ва изоҳлар муаллифи Абдулазиз Мансур. – Тошкент: Тошкент ислом университети, 2001.
3. Бурҳонуддин Марғинович. Ҳидоя шарҳ бидоятил мубтади: 2-жилд. - Тошкент: Hilol-Nashr, 2020.
4. Салоҳиддин Муҳиддин. Оила ва шаръий никоҳ одоблари. – Тошкент: Мовароуннаҳр, 1999.

5. Исломда аёллар ҳуқуқи. <https://islom.uz/maqola/8175>